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TOWARDS A UNIFIED APPROACH TO THE GOVERNANCE OF COMMERCIAL SPACE MINING

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ABSTRACT

The emergence of commercial space mining prospective has exposed a critical difference in approaches to the interpretation of certain core principles in the existing legal framework. This article argues that the current trajectory, characterized by two fundamentally opposed interpretations of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty and the 1979 Moon Agreement, leads to dangerous fragmentation. The first, restrictive approach views commercial resource extraction as a violation of the non-appropriation principle and both the concepts of the “province of all mankind” and the “common heritage of mankind.” The second, permissive approach distinguishes the OST's provisions from the Moon Agreement, justifying granting property rights over extracted resources.

This doctrinal divide has materialized in a patchwork of national laws, creating regulatory competition and undermining the OST's core principles. The article contends that a proactive move towards a unified international regime is necessary to avert conflict and inequality. It analyzes the theoretical underpinnings of the legal debate and its practical implications and evaluates potential pathways to unification. The consideration of these issues emphasizes that forging a single, coherent regulatory approach is essential for the sustainable and peaceful governance of space resources.

KEYWORDS: Space Mining, Equal Sharing, Common Heritage of Mankind, International Space Governance, Non-Appropriation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The commercialization of outer space has transformed a once purely scientific domain into a potential arena of economic competition. Today, human activities in space are featured by the rise of private space companies: what was once a state-only domain is increasingly being reshaped by private ventures like SpaceX and Blue Origin.³ The growing involvement of private actors in space activities has often been described as the beginning of a “new space race,” driven not only by states but increasingly by private investment in launch services, space tourism, and asteroid mining.⁴ What adds urgency to this debate is that space resources such as lunar Helium-3 could potentially meet humanity’s energy needs for up to 10,000 years.⁵ Yet, it is essential to declare that, without robust governance, clear decision rights and accountability, international oversight of environmental and safety risks, transparent data and AI standards for resource assessment, and coordination among governments, private actors, and scientific institutions, resource exploitation could instead trigger conflict, deepen global inequality, and cause irreversible environmental harm.

Advances in technology have made the extraction of extraterrestrial resources from celestial bodies technically feasible, while the emergence of private actors has intensified pressure on the existing legal framework. The 1967 *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty, OST)⁶ and the 1979 *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (the Moon Agreement)⁷ form the core of this framework, establishing the principles of freedom of exploration, non-appropriation, and use “for the benefit of all countries” that can challenge unilateral, profit-driven exploitation of extraterrestrial resources. However, the interpretation and interaction of these principles remain deeply contested.

Two doctrinal approaches to the question of space resource exploitation can be identified. The first, restrictive approach argues that the extraction and privatization of space resources by private actors violate international law, particularly the OST⁸ and the Moon Agreement,⁹ which emphasizes that exploitation should be governed by an international regime ensuring equitable sharing. Under this

³ Gomes, J. R., Devezas, T. C., Belderrain, M. C., Salgado, M. C. V., & de Melo, F. C. L. (2013). *The road to privatization of space exploration: What is missing*. 64th International Astronautical Congress. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289635460_The_road_to_privatization_of_space_exploration_What_is_missing.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Xu, F. (2020). The approach to sustainable space mining: issues, challenges, and solutions. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*. IOP Publishing. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338933560_The_approach_to_sustainable_space_mining_issues_challenges_and_solutions.

⁶ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. (1967). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>.

⁷ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. (1979). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/intromoon-agreement.html>.

⁸ This approach is represented, for example, by Lee, R. J. (2012). *Law and Regulation of Commercial Mining of Minerals in Outer Space*. Springer; Lyall, F. & Larsen, P. B. (2025). *Space Law: a Treatise*. Routledge; Ma, B. & Liu, J. (2021). Realistic Dilemma and Legal Countermeasures against the “Non-Appropriation” Principle in Outer Space Treaty. *Advanced Space Law, Vol. 7*, 45-55.

⁹ This approach is represented by Hobe, S. and Chen, K.-W. (2017). Legal status of outer space and celestial bodies. In R. S. Jakhu & P. S. Dempsey (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of space law*. Routledge; Yun, Z. (2020). A Multilateral Regime for Space Resource Exploration and Utilization. *Indonesian Journal of International Law: Vol. 1, No. 3*, 327–340; Lefeber, R. (2016). Relaunching the Moon Agreement. *Air and Space Law: Vol. 41, Issue 1*, 41-48.

approach, it is supposed that a new treaty regime for governing space resource activity is necessary¹⁰ and a potential model for it can be found in the regulation of deep seabed mining.¹¹ This article not only examines such options but also proposes other solutions for the problem of governing space resource activity in Section 4.

The second, permissive approach distinguishes the legal obligations in the two treaties, arguing that the OST's concept of the "province of all mankind" is broader¹² and does not prohibit commercial use, including commercial use by private actors in the process of privatization – terms which in this article are used interchangeably, unlike the Moon Agreement's "common heritage of mankind." The latter introduces explicit obligations for collective management of resources, while the former is broader and does not prohibit commercial use or require benefit-sharing. This doctrinal divide has materialized in a growing patchwork of national space-mining laws. Several states that are not parties to the Moon Agreement have adopted domestic legislation explicitly allowing private actors to extract and own space resources, while arguing that such activities remain consistent with the OST. Their interpretation relies on distinguishing between the treaty's prohibition of national appropriation of celestial bodies and the permissibility of ownership of extracted resources.

This fragmentation underscores a critical ambiguity in the current legal regime governing the extraction, ownership, and commercial use of outer space resources. Therefore, the international community faces the problem of how to avert a dangerous "first-come, first-served" system. Such a regime would effectively allow technologically advanced states and private corporations to monopolize the most valuable space resources, entrenching existing global inequalities and excluding less developed countries from meaningful participation. It could also incentivize a competitive rush to secure strategic locations, such as resource-rich regions of the Moon, thereby increasing the risk of geopolitical tensions and disputes over access and use. Moreover, without coordinated international rules, unregulated extraction could lead to environmental degradation of celestial bodies and undermine the principle that outer space should be used for the benefit of all humankind.

2. A BATTLE OF TWO APPROACHES: THEORETICAL PERCEPTION OF THE EXISTING LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The existing legal framework on the issue of exploitation of natural resources in outer space is formed primarily through the OST and the Moon Agreement. The number of states parties to these treaties differs greatly. The OST has been ratified by over 110 countries, including all the major space powers. No state has ever withdrawn, nor has any amendment been proposed.¹³ The Moon Agreement is a multilateral treaty opened for signature in 1979 following negotiations within the UN Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS).¹⁴ It currently has only 17 States Parties, and none of the major space-faring nations has ratified it. Notably, Saudi Arabia withdrew from the Moon Agreement in 2023, likely to facilitate the pursuit of commercial activities.¹⁵ While the treaty is legally binding on its parties,

¹⁰ Tronchetti, F. (2009). *The exploitation of natural resources of the Moon and other celestial bodies: A proposal for a legal regime* (Studies in Space Law, Vol. 4). Martinus Nijhoff Publishers.

¹¹ Masson-Zwaan, T. & Sundahl, M. J. (2024). National and international norms towards the governance of commercial space resource activity. In L. J. Smith, I. Baumann & S.-G. Wintermuth (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of commercial space law*. Routledge.

¹² Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11; Byers, M. & Boley, A. (2023). *Who Owns Outer Space? International Law, Astrophysics and the Sustainable Development of Space*. Cambridge University Press.

¹³ Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

¹⁴ Kopal, V. (2010). *The Progressive Development of International Space Law by United Nations and its Present System*. Proceedings of the International Institute of Space Law.

¹⁵ Wedenig, S.-M., & Nelson, J. W. (2023, 26 January). The Moon Agreement: Hanging by a thread? Institute of Air & Space Law, McGill University. <https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/article/moon-agreement-hanging-thread>.

its limited ratification weakens its perceived legitimacy and broader authority within the international community, particularly because key actors with the technological and economic capacity to exploit space resources are not bound by its provisions.

Presumably, this difference in the number of parties is due to the scope of the obligations established by these treaties. Some of the provisions of the Moon Agreement might become a legal barrier to resource extraction in space. In particular, Article 11 declares the Moon and its natural resources the “common heritage of mankind” and requires the establishment of an international regime to govern resource exploitation. This regime is expected to ensure the orderly development of resources, equitable sharing of benefits among states, and the prevention of monopolization. Additionally, the agreement requires international oversight of activities, environmental protection of the lunar environment, and the sharing of scientific information. For example, Article 11(5)-(7) calls for the establishment of an international regime to govern the exploitation of lunar natural resources and to ensure equitable sharing of benefits. Article 7(1) requires states to take measures to prevent disruption of the existing balance of the lunar environment and avoid harmful contamination. Furthermore, Article 6(1) encourages the sharing of scientific results obtained from lunar exploration with the international community. For private actors and technologically advanced states, these provisions could introduce regulatory uncertainty, limit exclusive control over extracted resources, and potentially require redistribution of economic benefits.¹⁶ However, certain obligations contained in the OST are also sometimes interpreted as limiting the possibility of exploiting space's natural resources.

In particular, Article I provides that the exploration and use of outer space shall be carried out “for the benefit and in the interests of all countries” and that outer space is the “province of all mankind,” which some scholars interpret as implying a requirement of equitable access or benefit-sharing. Article II prohibits national appropriation of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, by claims of sovereignty, use, or occupation, raising questions about whether exclusive control over resource-rich areas could amount to de facto appropriation. Additionally, Article IX requires states to conduct activities with due regard to the interests of other states and to avoid harmful contamination of celestial bodies, potentially limiting large-scale extraction activities that could interfere with other missions or damage the space environment.¹⁷

Thus, there are two approaches to the issue of compatibility of resource exploitation with the existing legal framework. Under the first, strictest approach, it is argued that the OST itself prohibits resource extraction in space.¹⁸ The second one focuses on the difference between the scope of obligations established by the OST and the Moon Agreement.¹⁹ Its proponents consider that only those states that have signed the Moon Agreement are bound by a number of obligations regarding space mining, while the OST does not address this issue.²⁰

To examine these two approaches, it is necessary to refer to the relevant provisions of the OST and the Moon Agreement. Three key issues will be: 1) the concepts of “the province of all mankind” and “common heritage of mankind”; 2) the principle of non-appropriation and its relevance to the exploitation of natural resources in outer space; 3) an obligation to take into account the corresponding interests of other states.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ Lee, *supra* note 8.

¹⁹ Hobe & Chen, *supra* note 9.

²⁰ Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

2.1. The concepts of “the province of all mankind” and “common heritage of mankind”

Article I(2) of the OST secures the freedom of exploration and use of outer space, freedom of access to all areas of celestial bodies and freedom of scientific investigation. ‘Freedom’ in this sense means that any entity that benefits from freedom does not need to seek permission to perform these activities from other governments.²¹

Entities entitled to this freedom are primarily states and, in accordance with Article XIII of the OST, international intergovernmental organizations. However, access by individuals, non-governmental organizations, and private enterprises is also possible.²² Conditions of these private actors’ access are established in Article VI of the OST, according to which states are obliged to issue authorization for activities of non-governmental entities in outer space and supervise them.

However, this freedom, secured by Article I(2), is not unlimited. Article I(1) of the OST means that the exploration and use of outer space, being the “province of all mankind,” is not aimed at serving only the interests of those states that have the technological capability to explore and utilize outer space, but those of all states, no matter what their degree of economic and scientific development is.²³

The Moon Agreement's regime differs from the general regime established by the OST. This difference is primarily reflected in Article 11(1) of the Moon Agreement, which introduces the concept of “the common heritage of mankind.” This concept, which is also applied to the resources of the seabed,²⁴ implies not only a prohibition on the appropriation of resources, but also the creation of an international regime for the management of these resources in the interests of all states, which is required by Article 11(5). Within the future framework of such a regime, the procedure and conditions for states to gain access to natural resources will be provided.

Thus, there are two different concepts of the “province of all mankind” and the “common heritage of mankind.” These concepts were always interpreted differently by developing countries (states which, unlike space-faring nations, have no relevant space capabilities and programmes)²⁵ and major space-faring states. For example, the US understood “common heritage of mankind” and “the province of all mankind” to be indistinguishable and, as such, they were considered an expansion of the principle of *res communis*, which means that something may not become the subject of appropriation by states.²⁶

For developing states, the “province of all mankind” principle meant that all nations had vested rights in common resources and should be shared equitably among them.²⁷ This brings the interpretation of the concept “province of all mankind” closer to the “common heritage of mankind” enshrined in the Moon Agreement. Therefore, both the US and developing countries have tended to mix the scope of obligations under these provisions, but only in different directions.

Some scholars take a position close to that expressed by developing states. They interpret the provision on the “province of all mankind” in the way that all states have the right to enjoy the benefits derived from space activities and should establish how to share them among all nations.²⁸

²¹ Hobe, S., Schmidt-Tedd, B. & Schrogl, K.-U. (Eds.). (2017). *Cologne commentary on space law, Volume I: Outer Space Treaty*. Berliner Wissenschafts-Verlag.

²² Ibid.

²³ Tronchetti, *supra* note 10.

²⁴ See Art. 136 of UNCLOS provided that “The Area and its resources are the common heritage of mankind.” https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf.

²⁵ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd & Schrogl, *supra* note 21.

²⁶ Gabrynowicz, J. I. (1992). The “Province” and “Heritage” of Mankind Reconsidered: A New Beginning. *Lunar and Planetary Institute*, 691-695. https://articles.adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1992lpsa.conf.691G/0000691_000.html.

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ Tronchetti, *supra* note 10.

This line of thought is also supported by the interpretation of the “province of all mankind” concept in accordance with other provisions of the OST. Even if the “province of all mankind” was not designed to lay down specifics of the distribution or sharing of the benefits and products derived from activities carried out in outer space, nor did it create an international entity charged with the power to make such distribution, this fact does not affect the obligatory nature of the concept.²⁹ The provisions of Article I(1) should be interpreted to mean that states should comply with their duty to carry out the exploration and use of outer space in the interest and for the benefit of all, through a voluntary sharing process and international cooperation.³⁰

Proponents of another approach, which is close in its results to what is expressed by major space-faring states, consider debatable the proper obligatory nature of the provision laid down in Article I(1) of the OST. It is formulated rather vaguely and can give the impression that it was meant to establish only general principles with no legally binding force.³¹ For example, Gabrynowicz argues that the “province of all mankind” provision of the OST is declaratory in nature and not a specific legal maxim, as is well supported in the legal literature.³²

However, analysis of the wording of the OST article shows that the “province” concept covers different activities. In general terms, this provision means that the exploration and use of outer space, being the “province of all mankind,” is not aimed at serving only the interests of those states that have the technological capability to explore and utilize outer space, but those of all states, no matter what their degree of economic and scientific development.³³ In contrast, the wording of the Moon Agreement demonstrates that “common heritage” refers to objects and resources. This difference in the meaning of the two concepts cannot be ignored. Thus, the interpretations which do not take this difference into account should not be accepted.

2.2. Non-appropriation principle

Article II of the OST establishes the principle of non-appropriation, which is reaffirmed by Article 11(2) of the Moon Agreement. However, neither provision specifies whether extracting and commercializing resources of celestial bodies can be in line with the principle.³⁴ It is noteworthy that Article II of the Outer Space Treaty has attained the status of customary international law; accordingly, even States that have not ratified the Treaty are expected to comply with its provisions.

The provisions containing the “prohibition of appropriation” clause may be interpreted in a literal manner. This position is based on the drafting history of the OST. The declarations of states made in response to draft Article II suggest that their intent was to exclude any possibility of acquiring property rights in outer space.³⁵

Moreover, proponents of this approach argue that the OST does not distinguish between celestial bodies and their resources, and, therefore, the resources of celestial bodies should be subject to the same prohibition of appropriation as the celestial bodies themselves.³⁶ They support this conclusion by citing Article 11 of the Moon Agreement, historically adopted as a development of the OST. As for the subjects, which claims are prohibited, Jakhu and Buzdugan stress that Article II must be understood to prohibit all

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Ibid.

³² Gabrynowicz, *supra* note 26 at 692.

³³ Tronchetti, F. (2015). Legal aspects of space resource utilization. In F. von der Dunk & F. Tronchetti (Eds.), *Handbook of space law*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

³⁴ Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

³⁵ Gorove, S. (1971). Limitations on the principles of freedom of exploration and use in outer space: Benefits and interests. In *Proceedings of the Thirteenth Colloquium on the Law of Outer Space*, 74-78.

³⁶ Ibid.

forms of appropriation, governmental or private, since allowing private claims would undermine the treaty's purpose.³⁷ This interpretation was later confirmed by legal scholars, who declared private property claims on celestial bodies legally void.³⁸

Other scholars insist on a narrow interpretation of the provisions of the OST according to which “a distinction can be drawn between the appropriation of a celestial body as a whole, and the appropriation of resources that have been extracted from it.”³⁹ It means that only a celestial body, as a whole, cannot be appropriated. Some scholars also suggest that the prohibition of national appropriation in Article II primarily applies only to states.⁴⁰ Interpreting it this way, private actors may gain property rights for resources in space.

The position of certain states may be found due to their participation in certain instruments, for example, in the Artemis Accords signed by 56 states. Section 10 of the Accords addresses space resource activity specifically by establishing that the extraction of space resources does not violate the ban on national appropriation under Article II of the OST. Therefore, states participating in the Artemis Accords support the conclusion that the non-appropriation principle does not prohibit the exploitation of space's natural resources.

2.3. The principle of due regard

In addition, Article IX of the OST obliges states to conduct activities in space, taking into account the corresponding interests of other states. In this regard, it establishes the mechanism of consultation. The principle of due regard “functions as a limitation to the freedom of exploration and use of outer space” provided for in Article I(2) of the OST.⁴¹ In this perspective, the freedom to use outer space means that a state is entitled to undertake activities that would not threaten the activities of other states.⁴² Thus, its wording and drafting history show that this clause was intended to prevent harmful interference, rather than to prohibit lawful operations.

Therefore, Article IX is procedural rather than prohibitive: it cannot be interpreted as a substantive restriction on resource extraction. As long as a state's resource-extraction activities are carried out with reasonable precautions and prior consultations where relevant, they remain consistent with Article IX.

3. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE AMBIGUITY IN APPROACHES

When it comes to the attitude of states toward the differences in approaches, those states that possess the technical capabilities for space mining will most likely take the least burdensome approach. This trend is also reflected in some states' national legislation. However, such a position entails dangerous practical consequences and is likely to undermine the effectiveness of the existing legal framework, giving it an interpretation that effectively deprives the provisions of their purpose.

³⁷ Jakhu, R., & Buzdugan, M. (2006). *The Role of Private Actors: Commercial Development of the Outer Space Resources, Including Those of the Moon and other Celestial Bodies: Economic and Legal Implications*. Workshop Proceedings: Workshop Convened at McGill University's Institute of Air & Space Law.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ de Zwart, M., Henderson, S. & Neumann, M. (2023). Space resource activities and the evolution of international space law. *Acta Astronautica*, 211, 155–162, at 156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.06.009>.

⁴⁰ Harris, D. J. (2004). *Cases and materials on international law*. Sweet & Maxwell.

⁴¹ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd & Schrogl, *supra* note 21 at 568.

⁴² Ibid.

3.1 *An overview of states' approach to the OST*

Some national laws, such as the 2015 U.S. *Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act*⁴³ and the 2017 *Luxembourg Law on the Exploration and Use of Space Resources*,⁴⁴ attempt to grant property rights to extracted resources. These states are not parties to the Moon Agreement but ratified the OST and most likely want to be secured by the “freedom” it provides. However, Xu emphasizes that the OST only clearly protects scientific investigation, not commercial exploitation.⁴⁵ Moreover, Article I’s mandate that space activities be conducted “for the benefit of all countries” is legally binding, yet its vague wording leaves benefit-sharing dependent on a state’s good faith.

This tension ultimately hinges on the very question of how Article I of the OST is interpreted in relation to Article II: whether the “use” permitted under Article I extends to the extraction and commercial sale of extraterrestrial resources. If so, national laws that recognize ownership of mined materials could arguably remain compatible with the OST. If not, such activities risk constituting indirect appropriation, undermining the non-appropriation principle that lies at the core of international space law. The unresolved nature of this issue has become the central legal fault line between proponents of open commercial exploitation and advocates of collective governance.

A textualist approach to this debate reads Article I and II strictly, concluding that any activity leading to ownership claims, directly or indirectly, is prohibited. This view, endorsed by Jakhu and Buzdugan, treats “use” as limited to exploration, research, and non-exclusive activities.⁴⁶ By contrast, a teleological or purpose-driven interpretation focuses on the OST’s objective of ensuring outer space is used for the benefit of all countries. Under this reasoning, if commercial exploitation is conducted transparently and its benefits are shared, it may still align with the OST’s spirit. A pragmatic perspective, increasingly reflected in national laws, argues that since space activities are now technologically and economically feasible, law must adapt to enable sustainable commercial use. The challenge, then, lies in reconciling these approaches to balance legal continuity with evolving realities of space commerce. This interpretive pluralism mirrors broader tensions in international law between stability and flexibility.

3.2 *The impact of the Moon Agreement*

With around 16,000 near-Earth asteroids considered easily accessible, space has become an increasingly attractive prospect for resource extraction and an additional source of minerals and materials.⁴⁷ Once states realized the realistic prospects of exploitation, the Moon Agreement was adopted. It sought to achieve a compromise by reaffirming the freedom of exploration and use of the Moon while committing parties to establish an international regime to govern the exploitation of lunar natural resources once such exploitation became feasible.⁴⁸

However, the Moon Agreement failed to gain broad adherence; few major spacefaring nations have ratified it.⁴⁹ As a result, several states have opted to develop their own national frameworks for space resource utilization, such as the United States, Luxembourg, the United Arab Emirates, and Japan. As Masson-Zwaan notes, rather than a patchwork of national laws, a unified international regime would be preferable to avoid legal fragmentation. She further argues that if ownership of space resources was

⁴³ U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act, Pub. L. No. 114-90, 129 Stat. 704 (2015). <https://www.congress.gov/114/plaws/publ90/PLAW-114publ90.pdf>.

⁴⁴ Grand Duchy of Luxembourg. (2017). *Law on the exploration and use of space resources* (Law of 20 July 2017). <https://space-agency.public.lu/dam-assets/publications/2017/07/Law-on-the-exploration-and-use-of-space-resources-2017.pdf>.

⁴⁵ Xu, *supra* note 5.

⁴⁶ Jakhu & Buzdugan, *supra* note 37.

⁴⁷ Casey, J. P. (2019, March 18). *A history of space mining: The future of resource extraction*. *Mining Technology*. <https://www.mining-technology.com/features/history-of-space-mining/>.

⁴⁸ Kopal, *supra* note 14.

⁴⁹ *Ibid*.

inherently illegal under the OST, the adoption of the Moon Agreement would make no sense, since that treaty explicitly contemplates the use and potential ownership of such resources.⁵⁰

3.3 The patchwork of national laws with dangerous consequences

Contemporary national frameworks build upon this expansive interpretation of the OST, seeking to legitimize private property rights through domestic legislation. National measures such as the U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act (2015) and Luxembourg's Law on the Exploration and Use of Space Resources (2017) both recognize ownership of extracted extraterrestrial materials, granting private entities the right to "possess, own, transport, use, and sell" resources they obtain in space.⁵¹ These laws exemplify an emerging trend of unilateral regulation, one that risks bypassing the collective governance framework envisioned by the Moon Agreement. Supporters claim that these statutes simply operationalize the OST's guarantee of the "free use" of outer space, while critics view them as a form of indirect appropriation that undermines the non-appropriation principle and exacerbates normative fragmentation in space law.⁵²

By consolidating their regulatory power at the national level, these states not only enable commercial actors but also challenge the international community to clarify where "use" ends and "appropriation" begins. The issue thus reflects a broader tension between state sovereignty, private enterprise, and the global commons ethos that underpins international space law.

National legislation on space resources has emerged unevenly across jurisdictions. The United States took the lead with its 2015 *Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act*,⁵³ explicitly allowing private ownership of extracted resources.⁵⁴ Luxembourg followed in 2017, motivated by its ambition to become a hub for "NewSpace" investment, offering a licensing regime and legal certainty for companies.⁵⁵ The United Arab Emirates adopted its 2019 *Space Activities Law*,⁵⁶ balancing commercial incentives with adherence to international obligations, requiring state authorization and supervision of private missions.⁵⁷ Japan's Space Resources Act (2021) similarly permits resource utilization but embeds it within a state approval framework.⁵⁸ These laws collectively signal a regulatory trend toward nationalization of space governance, where domestic regimes fill the vacuum left by the absence of an international authority. Yet, their divergence raises concerns about forum shopping and regulatory competition; companies might relocate to jurisdictions offering the most permissive terms. Scholars such as Masson-Zwaan and

⁵⁰ Masson-Zwaan, T. L. (2024). Some thoughts on the future of space law. In C.-J. Cheng (Ed.), *New trends in international law: Festschrift in Honour of Judge Hisashi Owada*, 377–394. Brill | Nijhoff.

⁵¹ U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act of 2015, *Pub. L. No. 114-90, 129 Stat. 704* (2015). <https://www.congress.gov/bill/114th-congress/house-bill/2262/text/pl>; Luxembourg. (2017, July 20). *Law of 20 July 2017 on the Exploration and Use of Space Resources*. Journal Officiel du Grand-Duché de Luxembourg, A–No. 674, 1–7. https://space-agency.public.lu/en/agency/legal-framework/law_space_resources_english_translation.html.

⁵² Jakhu & Buzdugan, *supra note 37*; Nasr, M., Hoffman, J., Masson-Zwaan, T., Rapp, D. & Newman, D. (2023, March 2). A policy framework for sustainable and equitable space resource utilization. SSRN. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4375679.

⁵³ U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act, *Pub. L. No. 114-90, 129 Stat. 704* (2015). <https://www.congress.gov/114/plaws/publ90/PLAW-114publ90.pdf>.

⁵⁴ U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act of 2015, *supra note 51*.

⁵⁵ Luxembourg, *supra note 51*.

⁵⁶ United Arab Emirates. (2019). Federal Law No. 12 of 2019 regulating the space sector (English translation). <https://www.moj.gov.ae/assets/2020/Federal%20Law%20No%2012%20of%202019%20on%20THE%20REGULATION%20OF%20THE%20SPACE%20SECTOR.pdf.aspx>.

⁵⁷ United Arab Emirates. (2019). *Federal Law No. (12) of 2019 on the Regulation of the Space Sector*. <https://www.moj.gov.ae/assets/2020/Federal%20Law%20No%2012%20of%202019%20on%20THE%20REGULATION%20OF%20THE%20SPACE%20SECTOR.pdf.aspx>.

⁵⁸ Japan. (2021). *Act on Promotion of Business Activities Related to the Exploration and Development of Space Resources (Act No. 76 of 2021)*. Japanese Law Translation. <https://www.japaneselawtranslation.go.jp/en/laws/view/4332/en>.

Tronchetti warn that such fragmentation risks creating a de facto property regime in outer space, driven by market logic rather than multilateral consensus.⁵⁹

Proponents of national resource laws argue that the OST permits “use” of resources without restriction. However, as Jakhu and Buzdugan emphasize, private entities do not enjoy autonomous rights under international law, they can only act under state authorization and continuous supervision.⁶⁰

This tension also plays out in practice: new private actors (e.g., Planetary Resources, Deep Space Industries) pursue asteroid mining projects, yet face serious barriers in law, technology, and economics, particularly the “lack of details for private missions” in the OST.⁶¹ Investors demand property rights guarantees before committing capital, but such guarantees currently conflict with international non-appropriation rules.⁶²

Xu sharpens this critique by identifying three key risks of a laissez-faire approach: 1) conflicts between states: a “first come, first served” system could trigger waste, disorder, and even militarization; 2) inequalities in benefit-sharing: spacefaring nations may accumulate disproportionate gains, while developing countries are excluded; 3) environmental contamination: activities could spread hazardous waste, debris, or even biological material, harming both outer space and Earth environments.⁶³

4. HOW TO AVOID THE NEGATIVE CONSEQUENCES?

In light of the presented doctrinal and practical approaches, the more widespread interpretation is that the OST does not establish any significant restrictions on the extraction of natural resources in space. Given that most of the states have signed the OST but not the Moon Agreement, some complicated problems arise. These include mining activities falling into a regulatory gray area, the ineffectiveness of some provisions of the Moon Agreement and even the OST, and the issue of a fragmented approach to the exploitation of natural resources in the national law of various states.

The doctrinal disagreement between restrictive and permissive interpretations of the OST not only shapes legal theory but also directly influences the policy options discussed in Section 3. Each proposed solution reflects an attempt to reconcile these competing interpretations. For example, proposals for universal adoption or amendment of the Moon Agreement largely reflect the approach, which emphasizes collective governance and equitable benefit-sharing. By contrast, reliance on national legislation or soft-law mechanisms aligns more closely with the permissive interpretation that allows commercial resource extraction within the existing framework of the OST. Consequently, the feasibility of the solutions discussed below depends largely on which interpretation of the current legal regime ultimately prevails.

4.1. Universal adoption of the Moon Agreement

The first one is to adopt the Moon Agreement universally and, most importantly, agree on the parameters for the exploitation of natural resources in space. The key to this will be the creation of a detailed regime, as required by Article 11(5), as otherwise, such a measure would be incomplete.

⁵⁹ Nasr, Hoffman, Masson-Zwaan, Rapp, & Newman, *supra* note 52; Tronchetti, *supra* note 10.

⁶⁰ Jakhu & Buzdugan, *supra* note 37.

⁶¹ Gomes, Devezas, Belderrain, Salgado, & de Melo, *supra* note 3 at 4-5.

⁶² Jakhu & Buzdugan, *supra* note 37.

⁶³ Xu, *supra* note 5.

At first glance, this option allows for the most consistent regulation, promoting a cohesive and coordinated international approach. However, even the states parties are in no hurry to implement the provisions of the Moon Agreement. Although they have thus committed to reaching an international agreement to govern commercial mining activities, it is unclear whether this means that no commercial activity can take place before such an agreement is in place⁶⁴. A Joint Statement was issued by the States Parties in 2008, proclaiming that the “common heritage of mankind” principle as embodied in the treaty does not constitute an obstacle to space mining initiatives⁶⁵.

Furthermore, the current trend regarding the Moon Agreement is that states (especially major space-faring nations) are not becoming parties to it and are even withdrawing from this treaty.⁶⁶ In this regard, the prospect of the Moon Agreement achieving at least the same level of acceptance as the OST does not currently appear realistic.

However, despite counterarguments regarding this option, the Moon Agreement remains a valid treaty directly addressing the issue of space resources, which must be taken into account. Furthermore, the interpretation given to it may not be final. The parties themselves can influence the interpretation of the treaty and, by subsequent agreement, modify this interpretation, making it more relevant and prudent in terms of “permissiveness.”

4.2. *The guidance of other regimes*

Given these unresolved tensions, scholars and policymakers have looked to other international regimes for guidance. Debates over the governance of space resources often turn into analogies with existing regimes for areas beyond national jurisdiction. One of the most frequently invoked examples is the *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)*⁶⁷ and its regulation of deep seabed mining.⁶⁸ Under UNCLOS Part XI, the resources of the seabed beyond national jurisdiction are declared the “common heritage of mankind,” and their exploration and exploitation are managed through the International Seabed Authority (ISA).⁶⁹ This body licenses mining activities, ensures benefit-sharing, and imposes environmental safeguards. Proponents argue that a similar model could be applied to outer space, where an international institution would coordinate licensing and guarantee that commercial exploitation does not lead to monopolization or inequitable distribution of benefits⁷⁰. Critics, however, note that the ISA regime has been politically contested and bureaucratically heavy, leading some spacefaring states to resist importing it wholesale into space law.⁷¹

Another relevant analogy is the Antarctic Treaty System (ATS). The 1959 *Antarctic Treaty*⁷² in Article IV declares Antarctica a demilitarized zone dedicated to peaceful purposes and scientific research, suspending rather than resolving sovereignty claims. It also guarantees freedom of scientific investigation

⁶⁴ Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶⁶ Wederlig, S.-M. & Nelson, J. W. (2023, January 26). *The Moon Agreement: Hanging by a thread?* McGill Institute of Air and Space Law. <https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/article/moon-agreement-hanging-thread>.

⁶⁷ United Nations. (1982). *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea*. United Nations. https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf.

⁶⁸ Tronchetti, *supra* note 10; Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

⁶⁹ International Seabed Authority. (2023). *Just and equitable management of the common heritage of humankind*. In *Secretary-General annual report 2023*. https://www.isa.org/jm/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/ISA_Secretary_General_Annual_Report_2023.pdf.

⁷⁰ Lodge, M. W. (2013). *The common heritage of mankind* (ISA Technical Study No. 3). International Seabed Authority, 15-19; Nandan, S. N., Lodge, M. W. & Rosenne, S. (2002). *The development of the regime for deep seabed mining*. International Seabed Authority, 45-52.

⁷¹ Freestone, D. (2009). Problems of the ISA regime for deep seabed mining. *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*, 24(3), 385-398; Boyle, A. (1983). Further development of the common heritage concept. *British Yearbook of International Law*, 53, 327-358.

⁷² Antarctic Treaty. (1959). *Treaty on Antarctica*. <https://www.ats.aq/e/ats.htm>.

and encourages international cooperation.⁷³ The ATS demonstrates that states can successfully cooperate in managing a territory rich in potential resources by prioritizing science, peace, and transparency over competition.⁷⁴ For space governance, the Antarctic model illustrates the possibility of maintaining international harmony while setting aside contentious sovereignty questions. Yet, unlike Antarctica, space mining involves direct commercial interests in extractable resources, which the ATS deliberately avoids.⁷⁵

These analogies highlight that cooperative governance of shared domains is possible, but designing a workable framework for space, where commercial incentives are far stronger, remains an unsolved challenge.

In any event, such regimes should be assessed on the basis not of potential copying but of analogy, taking into account all their work experience, with successes and failures.

4.3. The amendment of the Moon Agreement

The third option is to amend the Moon Agreement, eliminating the key contradictions between developing and space-faring states. In doing so, it is necessary to take into account the experience of UNCLOS and the 1994 Agreement, as well as the compromises that ultimately allowed states to reach a consensus. Furthermore, again, an agreement must be reached on a benefit-sharing regime, and a governing body similar to the ISA must be established for this purpose.

However, a significant obstacle to implementing this option may be the fundamental difference between UNCLOS and the Moon Agreement. UNCLOS initially featured a rather comprehensive and detailed system for mining technology transfer, funding, licensing, production control, and the equitable sharing of financial and other economic benefits.⁷⁶ It is “the most elaborated application of the concept of the common heritage of mankind in any instrument of international law.”⁷⁷ The Moon Agreement, by contrast, is merely a framework. The specific details for regulating the exploitation of natural space resources are to be agreed upon by the parties to the Moon Agreement through the process of establishing an international regime.⁷⁸ Consequently, if states are unwilling to even adopt the framework regulation, thereby forfeiting the opportunity to subsequently advance their vision for a more precise regulatory structure, this option appears unlikely.

Another obstacle is the limited influence of the Moon Agreement, which has very few ratifications and is not generally regarded as a strong instrument for regulating outer space activities. This, in turn, further diminishes both the perceived need for and the value of any amendment to the Moon Treaty.

4.4. Soft law with prospectives

The fourth option is regulation of exploitation through soft law. Today, non-binding forms are taking primacy through the work of the UN bodies.⁷⁹ These soft law instruments are resolutions of the UN General Assembly, as well as guidelines, such as the Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines of the UNCOPUOS.⁸⁰ In 2025, the UNCOPUOS presented an Initial draft set of recommended principles for

⁷³ *Ibid*, Articles II-III.

⁷⁴ Joyner, C. C. (1995). The Antarctic Treaty System and the Law of the Sea: Competing regimes in the Southern Ocean. *International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*, 10(3), 301–331.

⁷⁵ Dodds, K. & Hemmings, A. D. (2017). The Antarctic Treaty System and the politics of governance. In K. Dodds, A. D. Hemmings & P. Roberts (Eds.), *Handbook on the politics of Antarctica*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

⁷⁶ Lee, R.J. (2012). *Law and Regulation of Commercial Mining of Minerals in Outer Space*. Springer.

⁷⁷ *Ibid*. at 245.

⁷⁸ Moon Agreement, Article 11(5), *supra* note 7.

⁷⁹ Pecujlic, A.N. (2023). *The Space Law Stalemate: Legal Mechanisms for Developing New Norms*. Routledge.

⁸⁰ *Ibid*.

space resource activities.⁸¹ In their commentaries, some states not parties to the Moon Agreement acknowledge that its provisions are nevertheless part of the existing legal framework, which should be taken into account to develop the regulation.⁸²

Thus, some provisions of the Moon Agreement could become non-binding principles for states planning active exploitation of space resources. Although such principles are not obligatory, states can nevertheless bind themselves to them through certain acts: 1) to adopt national legislation which would implement the principles, making them obligatory for themselves on the national level; 2) to make declarations promising to follow these principles as mandatory (as unilateral acts); 3) through their consistent and widespread practice and perception of principles as obligatory, states can develop new rules of customary law.⁸³

These mechanisms would help legally obligate states to comply with a number of the Moon Agreement's provisions without their participation in the treaty itself. However, in this case, to truly establish a benefit-sharing regime (with or without a relevant authority), it would still be necessary to create multilateral regulation sooner or later, as national laws and unilateral acts could be inconsistent. Customary law also will not help with the description of the specific benefit-sharing procedure due to its nature not being as detailed as that of treaties.

Nevertheless, as reaching states' agreement on a universal approach is a complex and lengthy process, the first steps towards it can certainly be made in the form of soft law.⁸⁴

5. CONCLUSION

As this paper has demonstrated, the international community is fundamentally divided between two principal approaches – permissive and restrictive. Developing countries tend to adopt the restrictive approach, while space-faring nations embrace and operationalize the permissive approach through national legislation granting property rights over extracted resources.

The practical implications of this divergence are significant and potentially dangerous. The current trajectory, characterized by national laws, risks undermining the core principles of international cooperation that underpin not only the Moon Agreement, but even the OST. It creates a regulatory grey area where powerful states and private entities can advance their interests, potentially deepening global inequality and triggering political tensions. The international community, thus, needs a coherent and universally accepted regulatory framework.

Given the unlikelihood of the Moon Agreement achieving universal adoption and the political infeasibility of a comprehensive new treaty in the short term, the path forward must be pragmatic. A wholesale amendment of the Moon Agreement or the creation of a mandatory international regime akin to the ISA, while ideal in theory, faces substantial political hurdles. Therefore, the most viable immediate solution lies in the development of a soft law framework. This could take the form of a set of recommended principles, outlining at least some of the Moon Agreement's ideas.

⁸¹ Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space. (2025). *Initial draft set of recommended principles for space resource activities* (A/AC.105/C.2/L.339). United Nations. <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/v25/021/86/pdf/v2502186.pdf>.

⁸² United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2025). *Contribution of the Delegation of the Russian Federation to the Working Group on Legal Aspects of Space Resource Activities of the Legal Subcommittee of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space on elements for an initial draft set of recommended principles for space resource activities*. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/copuos/lsc/space-resources/DraftPrinciplesContributions/Russian_Federation_Contribution_to_the_WG_on_space_resources.pdf.

⁸³ Pecujlic, *supra* note 79.

⁸⁴ Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

In conclusion, the search for a unified approach to commercial space mining is a pressing necessity for the sustainable and peaceful future of human activities in outer space. Without such an approach, the commercialization of space risks replicating the historical patterns of terrestrial resource competition, thereby betraying the visionary spirit of international space law.